

Extraction of Chromium(VI) from Aqueous Ortho-Phosphoric Acid Solutions by Tri-*n*-Octylphosphine Oxide

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The extraction of chromium(VI) from ortho-phosphoric acid solutions by tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide has been studied. The nature of the extracted species is established.

THE use of phosphorous containing solvents¹⁻⁵ and other extracting systems⁶⁻⁸ for the extraction of chromium(VI) has been reported by several workers and the extracted species are identified as CrOX⁻ from HX solutions (X=Cl or Br) and as Cr₂O₇²⁻ from other mineral acid systems.

The present communication describes our studies on the extraction of chromium(VI) by tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide (TOPO) from ortho-phosphoric acid solutions in order to identify the extracted species.

Experimental

Materials : A 0.5M stock solution of chromium trioxide (E. Merck) was prepared and standardised with standard Fe²⁺ solution, using *n*-phenylanthranilic acid (NPA) as indicator and diluted as required.

TOPO (Eastman Kodak Company, Rochester, N.Y.), a white crystalline solid (Molecular weight 387) was used. 0.2M solution of TOPO in cyclohexane was prepared and employed in the studies. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade or purified by standard methods. Phosphorus-32 (carrier free) in the form of ortho-phosphoric acid in HCl was obtained from Isotope Division, B.A.R. C., Bombay.

Equipment : β⁻ activities of the solutions were measured using a liquid G.M. counting setup (ECIL, Hyderabad). The distribution of chromium (VI) was followed spectrophotometrically using a Unicam model SP600 spectrophotometer. Absorption spectra were taken on a Shimadzu Double beam spectrophotometer model UV-140.

Procedure : Chromium(VI) distribution studies were made using appropriate concentrations of chromium(VI) and ortho-phosphoric acid by equilibrating for about 3 to 5 minutes with an equal volume (10 ml) of 0.20M TOPO in cyclohexane which is preequilibrated with 1M ortho-phosphoric

acid solution. The amount of chromium(VI) upto 2g/l in the aqueous phase was determined spectrophotometrically by means of diphenyl carbazide⁹. Higher concentrations of chromium(VI) (>2g/l) were determined iodometrically.

The distribution of ortho-phosphoric acid as a function of chromium(VI) concentration was studied at 1.0M ortho-phosphoric acid concentration using ³²P as tracer using the same procedure. The non-exchange of ³²P activity between the aqueous H₃³²PO₄ and phosphorus in TOPO has been established before conducting these studies.

Results and Discussion

Extraction of Chromium (VI) as a Function of Acidity :

In order to find out the effect of acidity on the extraction of chromium(VI), extractions were carried out at various concentrations of ortho-phosphoric acid, using 0.20M TOPO in cyclohexane pre-equilibrated with 1M H₃PO₄, and 0.001M chromic acid. The distribution coefficients gradually increased with increasing acidity and were independent of acidity over the range 0.75M-1.5M ortho-phosphoric acid followed by a gradual fall upto 3M, beyond which chromium(VI) undergoes reduction to chromium(III).

Composition of the Extracted Species :

The composition of the extracted species was determined by the maximum loading experiments and also by the distribution ratio method¹⁰. The maximum loading of 0.20M TOPO with chromium(VI) at 1M aqueous acidity yielded a mole ratio of the [extractant] to [chromium (IV)]_{org}=unity. A plot of log [TOPO]_{org} vs log K_d in the distribution ratio method gave a straight line with a slope of 1.10. The method of least squares has been applied to the points of the plot and the slope of the straight-line was verified by calculation (slope =1.15). These studies show that the solvation

number with TOPO for chromium(VI) species in 1M ortho-phosphoric acid medium is unity.

Fig. 1. Distribution of phosphoric-acid as a function of Cr(VI).

In order to find out the association of phosphate with the extracted species, distribution studies were carried out from 1M phosphoric acid solutions tagged with ³²P tracer varying the aqueous chromium(VI) concentration and using 0.20M TOPO pre-equilibrated with 1M ortho-phosphoric acid (Fig. 1). It is seen that initially the concentration of ortho-phosphoric acid in the organic phase gradually increased with increasing chromium(VI) concentration, reaching a maximum value and remained constant, over the aqueous chromium(VI) concentration range, 0.05 to 0.15M and then gradually decreased. This clearly shows that the extracted chromium(VI) is present as a mixture of species containing predominantly phosphato-chromate.

Absorption Spectra :

The above findings are further confirmed by measurement of absorption spectra of the extracted species. The individual chromium(VI) species can be identified on the basis of their differences in absorption maxima in the U.V. region, ¹¹⁻¹³. The characteristic absorption maxima for Cr₂O₇²⁻ lie at 280 and 355 nm. The absorption spectra of chromium(VI) species extracted at various aqueous acid phase concentrations keeping the aqueous phase chromium(VI) concentration constant, showed absorption maxima at 280 and 355nm, but the molar extinction coefficient at 280nm changed gradually from ε=2200 to ε=1900 with a gradual increase in the concentration of phosphoric acid from 0.1M to 1.5M and remained constant thereafter.

In aqueous mineral acid systems chromium(VI) exhibits^{1,11-13} various equilibria giving rise to different species. The protonation of HCrO₄⁻ by the mineral acids was suggested by several workers¹⁴⁻¹⁷. In orthophosphoric acid solutions the species can be represented by the equilibrium,

Under the conditions the extractable species could be H₃CrPO₇, H₂CrO₄ and H₂Cr₂O₇. The extractability of the second and the third species with TBP has already been reported¹. It now appears that at high ortho-phosphoric acid concentrations the first species is formed to a significant extent leading to its extraction with TOPO. Further attempts to study the extraction of chromium(VI) in dilute ortho-phosphoric acid solutions with TOPO were not successful as the extractions were partial.

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